

Earth-abundant photocatalyst for H₂ generation from NH₃ with light-emitting diode illumination

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Abstract: Catalysts based on platinum group metals have been a major focus of the chemical industry for decades. We show that plasmonic photocatalysis can transform a thermally unreactive, earth-abundant transition metal into a catalytically active site under illumination. Fe active sites in a Cu-Fe antenna-reactor complex achieve efficiencies very similar to Ru for the photocatalytic decomposition of ammonia under ultrafast pulsed illumination. When illuminated with light-emitting diodes rather than lasers, the photocatalytic efficiencies remain comparable, even when the scale of reaction increases by nearly three orders of magnitude. This result demonstrates the potential for highly efficient, electrically driven production of hydrogen from an ammonia carrier with earth-abundant transition metals.

Surface plasmons excited by light in coinage metal nanoparticles (NPs) can generate both strong photothermal heating and nonequilibrium highly excited electrons or holes [hot carriers (HCs)] that can react with adsorbed molecules (1) and in turn provide an efficient way to transform light energy into chemical energy (2-4). Direct photocatalysis with metal NPs (5) has been demonstrated for numerous reactions, including H₂ dissociation on Au (1), O₂ dissociation on Ag (6), and propylene oxidation on Cu (7). However, despite their strong light-coupling properties (8), NPs composed solely of these metals do not provide active sites for the binding of adsorbates, which ultimately limits their catalytic properties.

Antenna-reactor (AR) complexes have been developed, typically consisting of a plasmonic NP (the antenna) decorated with reactor particles, such as islands, clusters, or single atoms of platinum group metals (PGMs) (9, 10). For example, a Cu-Ru AR complex efficiently photocatalyzed ammonia decomposition (11). As suggested by the Sabatier principle (12), Ru is an ideal binding site for this reaction because it binds the nitrogen intermediate species neither too strongly nor too weakly (13). The Cu-Ru photocatalyst has Ru reactors dispersed on Cu antennas, which generate HCs that enhance the reactivity of the photocatalyst and decrease reaction barriers by activating the Ru-N bond (11, 14). Although incorporating PGM reactors substantially improves photocatalytic performance, their scarcity and cost (15) drives efforts to replace them with more earth-abundant transition metals, especially for an industrial-scale reaction such as the decomposition of ammonia, which enables its use as a hydrogen carrier (16, 17). However, a metal such as Fe is far less reactive than Ru for this reaction when thermally driven because the Fe-N bond is so strong that the product fails to desorb (18).

We show that hot-carrier-facilitated activation on the surface of a plasmonic NP is as efficient for the Fe-N bond as for the Ru-N bond, resulting in a similarly large decrease in the activation barrier and notably similar photocatalytic reactivity under ultrafast pulsed laser illumination. Motivated by these findings, we investigate the feasibility of photocatalytically driving this reaction at room temperature using light-emitting diodes (LEDs) as the light source, scaling up the reaction by nearly three orders of magnitude in a custom photoreactor.

To compare photocatalytic Fe-N and Ru-N bond activation, we prepared Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru AR photocatalysts through a coprecipitation method (11, 19, 20), which is described in the Supplemental Materials (SM). This approach resulted in similar metal concentrations (table S1), indistinguishable morphologies (fig. S1) and comparable size distributions (fig. S2). Optical properties were also similar because the absorption is dominated by the plasmonic Cu NP instead of the lossy Fe or Ru surface sites (fig. S3). We further characterized the catalysts as described in SM. These similarities allowed us to compare the catalytic properties of Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru-ARs directly.

The catalytic properties of Cu-Fe-ARs were characterized both photocatalytically and thermocatalytically. Light-induced heating was monitored in operando with an infrared (IR) camera as a function of illumination power (see SM). Because of the porous nature of the powder sample, the emissivity of the sample powder was set to be 0.95 (21). The gaussian beam of the white-light laser (fig. S4) caused a similar distribution of the light-induced heating on the catalyst surface. Taking into consideration that part of the incident laser power was absorbed and converted to heat, temperature distribution in the catalyst was modeled (fig. S5B) using finite element analysis (see SM), which showed a trend similar to that of the experimental measurements. The power-dependent photocatalytic rates were correlated with temperature

through T_{\max} (power), the maximum surface temperature at a given power, which enabled a meaningful comparison with the thermocatalysis rate (Fig. 1A). Photocatalysis on Cu-Fe-ARs showed an increase in reaction rate of about 10,000 times compared with thermocatalysis. The turnover frequency increased from 0.00017 s^{-1} at 625 K to 1.7 s^{-1} ($0.466 \text{ mmol g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) at 200 mW (7.63 W/cm^2 , fig. S4) illumination ($T_{\max} \sim 625 \text{ K}$) on Cu-Fe and was comparable to the most efficient Ru-based thermocatalyst reported, which exhibited $0.435 \text{ mmol g}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ reactivity at 623 K (22). The Cu-Fe-AR was as efficient as the Cu-Ru-AR in photocatalysis despite its thermocatalytic reactivity being ~ 200 times lower (Fig. 1A). An $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2$ stoichiometric ratio of 3:1 was observed, indicating the absence of side reactions (fig. S6). Both photocatalysts showed stable H_2 production after 6 hours of illumination (fig. S7).

The measurement of reaction orders of the reactant and the apparent activation barriers can provide an increased understanding of the effect of HCs and the differences between Fe and Ru. The reaction order of ammonia increased under illumination for both Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru (Fig. 1B and fig. S8). Based on microkinetic analysis, an increase in reaction order implied a decrease in the coverage of surface N species (see SM, microkinetics analysis). This decrease suggested that HCs activated the metal-nitrogen bond and facilitated the desorption of surface species. Such a photochemical process is known as the desorption induced by electronic transition mechanism (23, 24). The apparent activation barrier (E_a) is defined as the sum of the activation barrier of the rate-determining step (RDS), the net enthalpy of the steps that produce species involved in the RDS, and a coverage-dependent term related to the enthalpy required to desorb reaction intermediates from active sites (25). For photocatalysis, the aforementioned T_{\max} were used in the Arrhenius equation to obtain the E_a . Cu-Fe showed a higher E_a (1.21 eV) than Cu-Ru (1.12 eV) in thermocatalysis, but this relationship was reversed in photocatalysis (Fig. 1B and fig. S9). The larger decrease of E_a on Cu-Fe-ARs compared with Cu-Ru-ARs was consistent with the greater enhancement in photocatalysis.

Wavelength dependence studies that correlate the incident wavelength with the output reaction rate also suggested that a contribution from HCs was essential. Photocatalytic reactivities of Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru peaked at $\sim 475 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 1C), which was far from the optical absorption peak at $\sim 570 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 1C, inset). This difference further confirmed that photocatalytic reactivity was not a purely thermal effect. We used a simple HC injection model (see SM) to simulate the wavelength-dependent behavior. HC injection occurs when HCs scatter into metal-adsorbate orbitals (MAOs) (Fig. 1D, inset). For example, hot electrons can scatter into antibonding MAOs to form transient negative ion states (6). The normalized HC injection rate agreed with experiments for an MAO centered at 0.5 eV above the Fermi energy E_F (Fig. 1D). Our model suggests that the quantum efficiency of incident photons depended more on the generation of HCs at the MAO energy level, rather than on the optical absorption or the total HC generation rate predicted by near-field enhancement. The MAO energy level is defined by the electronic structure of the adsorbate, which is also influenced by the image potential at the metal NP surface (26) (fig. S10). For the previously reported Cu-Ru-AR—which had a lower Ru loading and smaller average NP size (11)—the electronic structure and the image potential were different, which resulted in a down-shift of the MAO energy and a red-shift of the reactivity peak.

To understand the microscopic reaction mechanism on Cu-Fe-AR, we used embedded correlated wave function (27, 28) theory to calculate potential energy surfaces (PESs) projected along minimum-energy paths (MEPs, characterized by the reaction coordinates). Two possible RDSs were considered on Cu-Fe, Cu-Ru, and pure Cu surfaces: dissociative adsorption of NH_3 and associative desorption of N_2 . NH_3 first binds molecularly to the catalytic sites with an adsorption energy of 1.81 eV on Cu-Fe, 1.26 eV on Cu-Ru, and 0.82 eV on Cu at the embedded complete-active-space second-order perturbation theory (emb-CASPT2) (29, 30) level (Fig. 2A). The ground-state barrier for adsorbed NH_3 (NH_3^{ads}) dissociation to adsorbed NH_2 and H ($\text{NH}_2^{\text{ads}} + \text{H}^{\text{ads}}$) is 1.20 eV with a quintuplet-to-triplet crossing at $s \sim 6.7 \text{ \AA}$ (Fig. 2B). The barrier would be 1.36 eV if it remained on the quintuplet PES (fig. S11). The same N-H bond dissociation in NH_3^{ads} has a barrier of 1.35 eV on Cu-Ru and 2.06 eV on pure Cu, showing the power of alloying with Fe or Ru. Upon excitation, NH_3^{ads} (at $s = 5 \text{ \AA}$) reaches the third quintuplet excited state on Cu-Fe (Fig. 2B, solid arrow). The resulting effective excited-state barrier for NH_3^{ads} dissociation to $\text{NH}_2^{\text{ads}} + \text{H}^{\text{ads}}$ on Cu-Fe is 0.53 eV with a quintuplet to triplet crossing at $s \sim 6.4 \text{ \AA}$, whereas it is 0.95 eV on Cu-Ru (14) and 0.32 eV on pure Cu (note that the RDS on pure Cu becomes associative desorption of N_2 upon excitation, see below) (31).

The associative desorption of N_2 on Cu-Fe (Fig. 2C) was experimentally observed to be the RDS. The ground-state barrier for this step was indeed rate limiting: 2.67 eV with a crossing from triplet to quintuplet at $s \sim 3.2 \text{ \AA}$ (Fig. 2D and fig. S12). The corresponding barrier was 2.84 eV on Cu-Ru but only 1.48 eV on pure Cu. Because of the lower barrier on pure Cu, N^{ads} potentially could migrate from Fe to Cu sites favored by entropy increase (fig. S13), then desorb with a smaller barrier. Upon excitation, the system could be promoted to the ninth excited state and then traverse a manifold of closely spaced spin states to reach the triplet ground state on Cu-Fe (Fig. 2D, inset). The resulting excited-state barrier for associative desorption of N_2 is 0.50 eV whereas it is 0.65 eV on both Cu-Ru (14) and pure Cu (31).

This model provides a qualitative description of both ground-state thermocatalysis and excited-state photocatalysis (Fig. 2E). The activation barriers of both steps on Cu-Fe decreased considerably upon excitation, revealing why the reaction rate was greatly enhanced upon illumination. The resulting barriers were smaller (0.53 and 0.50 eV) than those on Cu-Ru (0.95 and 0.65 eV) because the excited transition states had lower energies caused by extensive mixing of different spin manifolds. Note that the measured apparent E_{as} were coverage dependent and differed from calculated E_{as} of the elementary steps, which were calculated only for the low-coverage limit. Moreover, the actual Fe reactor NP could be in a more complex geometry than our single-atom catalyst model. Nevertheless, the matching theoretical and experimental qualitative trends in the nonthermal effects, both increasing reaction orders and decreasing E_{as} , clearly showed the distinct advantages of HC-based plasmonic photocatalysis over thermocatalysis.

Photocatalysis with antenna-reactor catalysts made by abundant materials, ideally fueled by renewable electricity, potentially represents a practical route for sustainable production of fuels and major commodity chemicals, replacing fossil fuel based heat sources with low-cost photon sources such as LEDs. A continuous decline in the cost of renewable electricity (currently as low as 5¢ per kWh^{-1} in many parts of the world) (32) along with substantial and continuous improvements in the efficiency and cost of LEDs (33) could make renewable photons inexpensive and abundant (see SM). These innovations further motivate the development of plasmonic

photocatalysis for industrially relevant reactions (34). The differences in the temporal structure of an ultrafast pulsed laser source and continuous-wave LEDs were also substantial and could provide valuable insight into the relative contributions of HCs and photothermal heating for different photocatalysts for the same chemical reaction.

To that end, we investigated visible-light-driven NH_3 decomposition using Cu-Ru and Cu-Fe photocatalysts for gram-scale H_2 production in an LED-based, high-throughput photoreactor (Syzygy Plasmonics Inc.) (Fig. 3). The photoreactor included an annular reaction cell surrounded by a bank of customized 470-nm LEDs (Fig. 3A). The Cu-Fe catalyst (3.7 g, 60–120 mesh size, that is, 125–250 μm) was packed into the space between the two concentric tubes (4.6 cm bed length and 0.5 cm bed depth) in the reaction cell. The gram-scale photoreactor design was fairly optimized for efficient light utilization and mass transfer based on the physical properties of the catalyst (mesh size), photon penetration depth (typically $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) (35), and photothermal heat diffusion to achieve optimum photocatalytic reaction rates and energy efficiency.

We performed photocatalytic measurements using this LED light source without external heating. Illumination resulted in efficient ammonia decomposition for both the Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru photocatalysts (Fig. 3B). Compared to the photocatalytic reactivity of the two catalysts under pulsed laser illumination (Fig. 1A), photocatalysis driven by LED irradiation also resulted in similar reactivities of the two photocatalysts, but with a slightly higher reactivity for the Cu-Ru catalyst. A greater contribution from photothermal heating in the continuous wave LED case than under irradiation with ultrafast laser pulses would be expected, given that the latter is more efficient in the generation of HCs (23, 24). The Cu-Fe catalyst still exhibits a very high photocatalytic reactivity under LED illumination, up to 72% NH_3 conversion and 14 g H_2 per day under the delivered power of 180 W at a feed space velocity of 487 hr^{-1} .

We also investigated NH_3 conversion, H_2 production rates, and energy efficiency for the Cu-Fe catalyst as a function of NH_3 space velocity under a constant LED power of 140 W (4.1 Wcm^{-2}) (Fig. 3C). As shown, increasing the NH_3 feed hourly space velocity (SV) by more than six times (from 160 to 1060 hr^{-1}) only led to a $\sim 40\%$ feed conversion drop (from 77 to 47%). Accordingly, this resulted in a four-fold increase in H_2 production from ~ 4.5 to ~ 18 g H_2/day , and thus a notable improvement in the photon-to- H_2 conversion efficiency from 4.3 to 15.6%. The energy efficiency here considered the efficiency of the absorbed photons being converted to chemical energy by comparing the heat values of NH_3 and H_2 (see SM). However, when the losses associated with LED drivers, diode efficiency, and photons escaping the reactor were also considered, the input (wall plug) electricity-to- H_2 efficiency would be lower (from 1.5 to 5.6%) (fig. S14). Photocatalytic stability tests were also performed on the Cu-Fe catalyst at 54 % NH_3 feed conversion, showing excellent stability with no signs of decreased activity throughout an illumination period of 67 hours (Fig. 3D).

Currently, there are no commercial thermal ammonia decomposition plants for H_2 production in operation and industrial ammonia cracking has been primarily applied within the metallurgy industry using an electrically heated furnace with Ni catalysts operating at 900 $^\circ\text{C}$ (36). Hence, achieving those reactivity metrics by using a relatively small volume ($\sim 11 \text{ cm}^3$) of an earth-abundant photocatalyst in a gram-scale photoreactor with commercially available LEDs demonstrates the potential scalability of electrified photocatalysis with LED illumination for producing low-temperature green H_2 from NH_3 . Based on the H_2 production rates on the Cu-

Fe catalyst at SV 1060 hr⁻¹, we estimate an energy usage of 560 kWh/kg H₂. The input energy demand for chemical production, however, is strongly influenced by the size of the plant and other factors. Hence, we expect that photoreactor scaling with improved design, process optimization, and LED efficacy improvement could substantially reduce the required input electricity at large scale, that is, down to a few tens of kWh/kg H₂. This is critical to the economic viability and widespread adaptation of NH₃ as a green H₂ carrier in the future (see SM). It also requires technologies for producing green NH₃ such as electro- and photochemical approaches—which are currently in early stages of development—to become mature and economically viable with an energy demand at scale competitive to that of the energy consumption of state of the art Haber-Bosch plants (9 to 15 kWh/kg NH₃) (37).

Alternatively, H₂ can be stored in materials, such as metal hydride and sorbent materials, with subsequent release at high temperature on demand. State of the art material-based H₂ storage is still under development, with the main target being small-scale applications in light-duty vehicles and opportunities for portable power generation. However, the projected cost of H₂ (US dollars per kilogram of H₂) produced in this way is very high as indicated by the US Department of Energy (DOE)'s ultimate target cost of \$266 per kg of H₂ (38). The overarching goal of advancing H₂ storage materials is to reduce costs by discovering materials that can reduce the required storage pressure and temperature for H₂ release and increase gravimetric or volumetric storage capacity. The gravimetric H₂ storage capacity of NH₃ (17.6 wt %) already exceeds that of the H₂ storage materials currently investigated by the DOE Fuel Cell Technologies Office. Moreover, eliminating the need for external heating through photocatalysis of ammonia decomposition as shown here is consistent with the DOE's ultimate system target (fig. S15).

We have demonstrated that Cu-Fe, an otherwise poor thermocatalyst, can serve as an excellent photocatalyst for NH₃ decomposition with an efficiency similar to that of Cu-Ru under short-pulse laser illumination. The hot carriers, once created, stimulate the formation of adsorbate-metal excited states, activate the metal-adsorbate bond, decrease apparent and elementary step activation barriers, clean occupied active sites, and facilitate product desorption, thereby enhancing both the reactivity and stability of Cu-Fe relative to the thermal case. Under continuous-wave LED illumination, Cu-Fe showed a similarly high efficiency to Cu-Ru, but the greater photothermal heating resulted in a slightly greater reactivity of Cu-Ru. This study suggests that transition metals, traditionally regarded as unsuitable for conventional thermocatalysis, may be relevant substrates for plasmonic photocatalysis and also demonstrates that photocatalysis can be efficiently performed with inexpensive LED photon sources. These results strongly motivate the study of more abundant metals that can serve as highly efficient reactive sites for plasmonic antenna-reactor photocatalysis.

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Data and materials availability: Additional data sets generated and/or analyzed during the current study that are not included in this published article (and its supplementary information files) are available at open-access repository (39).

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Supplementary Materials

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Materials and Methods

Figs. S1 to S23

Table S1

References (40–94)

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Figure 1. The ammonia decomposition reaction on Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru-AR photocatalysts. (A) Comparison of photocatalysis and thermocatalysis for both ARs. Reactions were performed under differential reactor conditions (<2% reactant conversion), to avoid mass transfer limitations. Error bars represent standard deviations among three independent measurements. (B) Macroscopic kinetics studies: (top) the reaction orders of reactant, (bottom) the apparent activation barrier, E_a . A power of 0 mW refers to thermocatalysis. (C) Wavelength-dependent reaction rates. (Inset) Optical absorption spectra. (D) Calculated wavelength-dependent hot carrier injection rate with the antibonding orbital (ϵ_0) positioned at 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 eV above Fermi level E_F . (Inset) Schematic of the HC injection model.

Figure 2. First-principles quantum mechanical studies of photocatalytic ammonia decomposition. (A) Plane-wave density-functional theory with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof exchange-correlation functional and D3 Becke-Johnson damping corrections (DFT-PBE-D3BJ) optimized structures along the MEP for NH_3 dissociative adsorption on a Cu-Fe alloy surface. (B) Ground and excited-state emb-CASPT2 PESs along the MEP in (A) for the spin eigenstates: singlet (green), triplet (red), quintuplet (blue). Solid, straight, orange arrows represent vertical excitation and de-excitation, and dashed, curly, orange arrows represent productive (thermal) pathways. (C) The DFT-PBE-D3BJ optimized structures along the MEP for associative desorption of N_2 . (D) Ground and excited-state emb-CASPT2 PESs along the MEP in (C) for the spin eigenstates, (inset) enlarged PESs at 0 to 4 Å. (E) Schematic comparison of the energy landscape for photocatalysis (excited states) and thermocatalysis (ground state) on Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru. Red arrows refer to electronic excitation on Fe-N, and blue to Ru-N. Only the two possible RDSs are included for simplicity; migrations of nitrogen species are not considered for the same reason.

Figure 3. Electrified photocatalysis of ammonia decomposition for gram-scale H_2 production. (A) Photograph of the reaction cell (left) and the photocatalytic platform (right) using LEDs at 470 nm for ammonia decomposition. The reaction cell consisted of two concentric tubes of different diameters, with the catalyst (~0.5 cm bed thickness) filled in between them. (B) Ammonia conversion and corresponding H_2 production rates on the Cu-Fe and Cu-Ru catalysts as a function of delivered LED power at ammonia space velocity 487 hr^{-1} , which is defined as the volumetric flow rate of ammonia divided by the volume of the catalyst (11 cm^3). (C) Ammonia conversion, H_2 production, and energy efficiency as a function of the feed space velocity during ammonia decomposition on the Cu-Fe catalyst under illumination power 140 W. (D) Long-term photocatalytic ammonia decomposition on the Cu-Fe catalyst under illumination power 137 W (light on at time = 0). In each case, measurements were performed using ~3.7 g catalyst (60 to 120 mesh size, that is, 250 to 125 μm) and without supplying external heating.